

ACCELERATED TESTING METHOD FOR DURABILITY OF CFRP

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ABSTRACT

This study assessed an accelerated testing methodology for measuring CFRP laminate durability. First, the formulation for time and temperature dependent statistical static, creep, and fatigue strengths for CFRP laminates was done based on the matrix resin viscoelasticity. Second, these strengths of unidirectional CFRP were predicted statistically using the formulated equations. The predicted ones were compared with experimental data measured from resin-impregnated CFRP strands as the specimens of unidirectional CFRP. Finally, the statistical long-term tensile static, creep, and fatigue strengths are discussed in terms of the role of the matrix resin viscoelasticity.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) have been used for the primary structures of airplanes, ships, automobiles, and other vehicles, for which high reliability must be maintained during long-term operation. Therefore, an accelerated testing methodology is strongly anticipated for long-term life prediction of CFRP structures exposed to actual environmental temperatures, water, and other influences.

The mechanical behavior of CFRP matrix resin exhibits time and temperature dependence, so-called viscoelastic behavior, not only above the glass transition temperature T_g , but also below T_g . Consequently, it can be presumed that the mechanical behavior of CFRP depends strongly on time and temperature. Our earlier reports presented an accelerated testing methodology for predicting the life of fiber-reinforced polymers (FRP) based on the matrix resin viscoelasticity [1].

The tensile strength along the longitudinal direction of unidirectional CFRP constitutes important and basic data for the reliable design of CFRP structures. The authors developed a testing method for the creep, fatigue, and static strengths at elevated temperatures using resin-impregnated carbon fiber strands (CFRP strands) [2].

As described in this paper, first, the formulation for time and temperature dependent statistical static, creep, and fatigue strengths for CFRP laminates is performed based on the matrix resin viscoelasticity. Second, these strengths of unidirectional CFRP are inferred statistically using the formulated equations. The predicted values are compared with experimental data measured using resin-impregnated CFRP strands as unidirectional CFRP specimens. Finally, the inferred long-term tensile static, creep, and fatigue strengths are discussed in terms of the role of the matrix resin viscoelasticity.

2 FORMULATIONS FOR STATISTICAL CFRP STRENGTHS

The time and temperature dependent static, creep, and fatigue strengths of CFRP are formulated based on the matrix resin viscoelasticity by assuming that the CFRP deformation is perfectly controlled by the high elasticity of carbon fibers.

First, the statistical time and temperature dependent static strength of CFRP can be formulated with the following equation based on two conditions: A and B.

Condition A: Failure probability is independent of the temperature and load histories.

Condition B: Time-dependent and temperature-dependent strength is controlled by the matrix resin viscoelasticity.

$$\log \sigma_s = \log \sigma_0 + \frac{1}{\alpha} \log[-\ln(1 - P_f)] + n_R \log \left[\frac{E_s^*(t, T)}{E_r(t_0, T_0)} \right] \quad (1)$$

In this equation, P_f signifies the failure probability, t denotes the failure time, t_0 represents the reference time, T is the temperature, T_0 stands for the reference temperature, and σ_0 and α respectively denote the scale parameter and the shape parameter on the Weibull distribution of static strength. In addition, n_R is the viscoelastic parameter. E_r and E_s^* respectively represent the relaxation and viscoelastic moduli of matrix resin. The viscoelastic modulus E_s^* for the static load with a constant strain rate is presented by the following equation.

$$E_s^*(t, T) = E_r(t/2, T) \quad (2)$$

Rosen's model is well known as the failure model for the tensile static strength under the longitudinal direction of unidirectional fiber composites [3]. Viscoelastic parameter n_R in Equation (1) can be shown by the following equation based on our earlier work [4] as shown below.

$$n_R = 1/2\alpha_c \quad (3)$$

Therein, α_c signifies the shape parameter of tensile strength of a single carbon fiber.

The statistical creep strength σ_c can be ascertained by shifting the master curve of static strength with $\log A$ based on Christensen's theory for viscoelastic crack kinetics [5]. Therefore, the master curve of creep strength can be represented by the following equation as shown below.

$$\log \sigma_c = \log \sigma_0 + \frac{1}{\alpha} \log[-\ln(1 - P_f)] + n_R \log \left[\frac{E_c^*(t, T)}{E_r(t_0, T_0)} \right] \quad (4)$$

In that equation, E_c^* represents the viscoelastic modulus for a constant stress load, as shown by the following equation.

$$E_c^*(t, T) = E_s^*(At, T) = E_r(At/2, T) \quad (5)$$

The shifting amount $\log A$, as ascertained by the slope of the logarithmic static strength–logarithmic failure time curve is shown by the following equation.

$$\log A = \log \left(1 + \frac{1}{k_R} \right), \quad k_R = n_R m_R \quad (6)$$

Therein, m_R is the slope of logarithmic creep compliance of matrix resin against logarithmic time.

We propose the formulation of statistical fatigue strength of CFRP σ_f with fatigue degradation parameter F_f based on the matrix resin viscoelasticity, as shown in the following equation.

$$\log \sigma_f = \log \sigma_0 + \frac{1}{\alpha} \log[-\ln(1 - P_f)] + n_R \log \left[\frac{E_f^*(t, T)}{E_r(t_0, T_0)} \right] - F_f [\log(2N_f)] \quad (7)$$

The viscoelastic modulus E_f^* is shown by the following equation for the cyclic load for the case in which the stress ratio of the minimum stress / the maximum stress is zero, assuming that the matrix resin deformation in CFRP during cyclic load is perfectly constrained by the carbon fiber rigidity.

$$E_f^*(t, T) = \frac{1}{2} \left[E_r \left(\frac{1}{4f}, T \right) + E_r \left(\frac{N_f}{f} - \frac{1}{4f}, T \right) \right], \quad N_f = ft \quad (8)$$

Fatigue degradation parameter F_f , as the function of the number of cycles to failure N_f , is obtainable by the following polynomial function of $\log(2N_f)$, which is determined experimentally.

$$F_f[\log(2N_f)] = a[\log(2N_f)]^3 + b[\log(2N_f)]^2 + c[\log(2N_f)] \quad (9)$$

The fatigue strength at $N_f = 1/2$ is equal to the static strength when failure time t is equal to $1/2f$.

3 CFRP STRAND MOLDING AND TESTING

Carbon fibers used for this study are high-strength PAN-based carbon fiber (T300-3000; Toray Industries Inc.). Their mechanical properties, as referred from catalogs, are presented in Table 1.

Figure 1 shows that the CFRP strands combined with the carbon fiber and a general purpose epoxy resin (jER828; Mitsubishi Chemical Corp.) were molded using a filament winding system developed by the authors [2]. Actually, 200 specimens for the CFRP strands were molded at one time using this system. The epoxy resin composition and the CFRP strand curing conditions are presented in Table 2. The gage lengths of CFRP strands are approximately 200 mm, as shown in Figure 2. The grip mechanisms to the CFRP strands were developed for static, creep, and fatigue tests conducted at various temperatures.

The glass transition temperature $T_g = 160$ °C of the epoxy resin were ascertained from the peak of the loss tangent against temperature at 1 Hz using a Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) testing machine. The fiber volume fraction $V_f = 55\%$ of CFRP strand is ascertained from the CFRP strand weight.

The original static testing machine with the temperature chamber shown in Figure 3 can achieve a constant elongation rate in a wide range and constant temperatures of 25–170 °C. Twenty sets of the original creep testing machines and five sets of the original fatigue testing machines with temperature chambers shown in this figure can respectively realize a constant load and a constant cyclic load in the maximum load 1 kN and constant temperatures 25–150 °C.

Carbon fiber	Density [g/cm ³]	Tex [g/km]	Elastic modulus [GPa]	Tensile Strength [MPa]
T300-3000	1.76	198	230	3,530

Table 1: Carbon fiber and the mechanical properties

CFRP strand	Carbon fiber	Composition of resin (weight ratio)	Cure schedule
T300/EP	T300-3000	Epoxy: jER828 (100) Hardener: MHAC-P (103.6) Cure accelerator: 2E4MZ (1)	70 °C × 12 h + 150 °C × 4 h + 190 °C × 2 h

Table 2: Composition and cure schedule of CFRP strand

Figure 1: Molding system for CFRP strands as specimens.

Figure 2: Configuration of CFRP strand specimens.

Figure 3: Static, creep, and fatigue tests for CFRP strands.

4 STATISTICALLY INFERRED STATIC STRENGTH OF CFRP STRAND

The dimensionless creep compliance D_c/D_{c0} measured at various temperatures is shown in the left panel of Figure 4. Long-term D_c/D_{c0} at $T = 120$ °C is obtained by horizontally shifting those at various temperatures, as shown in the right panel of this figure [6]. The reference time and temperature are selected for this study as $t_0 = 1$ min and $T_0 = 25$ °C. Creep compliance D_{c0} at the reference temperature and reference time is 0.33 GPa^{-1} . The relaxation modulus $E_r(t, T)$ is determined simultaneously as the inverse of creep compliance. The temperature condition and $E_r(t_0, T_0)$ at $t_0 = 1$ min and $T_0 = 25$ °C is 3.0 GPa. The determined relaxation modulus and time-temperature shift factor for matrix resin are used as the viscoelastic moduli in Equations (1), (4), and (7).

Figure 4: Dimensionless creep compliance and time-temperature shift factor of matrix resin.

4.1 Static strength of CFRP strands at various temperatures

Static tension tests for CFRP strand were conducted at five temperature of 25 °C, 120 °C, 135 °C, 150 °C, and 170 °C with cross-head speed of 2 mm/min. The CFRP strand tensile strength σ_s is obtained using the following equation.

$$\sigma_s = \frac{W_{\max}}{t_e} \rho \quad (10)$$

In this equation, W_{\max} represents the maximum load [N]. Additionally, ρ and t_e respectively denote the density of the carbon fiber [kg/m^3] and the tex of the carbon fiber strand [$\text{g}/1000 \text{ m}$]. Figure 5 shows the static strength versus temperature for the CFRP strands. Static strengths for CFRP strands decrease markedly with increasing temperature.

The Weibull distributions for static strength at various temperatures are depicted in Figure 6 for the CFRP strand. In this figure, α_s is the CFRP strand shape parameter; β_s is the scale parameter. Although the scale parameter decreases according to the temperature rise, the shape parameter maintains an almost constant value for the CFRP strand to the temperature raise. Shape parameter α_s and scale parameter β_s at $T = 25$ °C in this figure can be inferred as shape parameter α , scale parameter σ_0 of static strength at the reference temperature $T_0 = 25$ °C and the reference failure time $t_0 = 1$ min used in Equation (1).

Figure 5: Static strengths of CFRP strand against temperature.

Figure 6: Weibull distributions of static strength of CFRP strand at various temperatures.

4.2 Static strength of CFRP strand against viscoelastic compliance of the matrix resin

Figure 7 presents the dimensionless static strength σ_s/σ_0 of a CFRP strand against the dimensionless viscoelastic modulus of matrix resin E_s^*/E_{r0} simultaneously and temperatures for CFRP strands. The relation of σ_s/σ_0 against E_s^*/E_{r0} can be represented as one solid straight line with the slope of n_R , which is the viscoelastic parameter in Equation (1), as obtained from Christensen’s model of viscoelastic crack kinetics. The dotted line in this figure is a straight line with the slope of viscoelastic parameters n_R obtained by substituting shape parameter α_c of single carbon fiber strength based on Rosen’s model [4].

Figure 7: Static strength of CFRP strand against viscoelastic modulus of matrix resin.

4.3 Master curve of static strength for CFRP strand

All parameters in Equation (1) for the master curve of static strength are found for the CFRP strand, as shown in Table 3: shape parameter α and scale parameter σ_0 of static strength at the reference temperature of $T_0 = 25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; reference failure time $t_0 = 1 \text{ min}$; viscoelastic parameter n_R ; and the dimensionless viscoelastic modulus of matrix resin E_s^*/E_{r0} found from the creep compliance of matrix resin shown in Figure 4. The master curve of statistical static strengths for CFRP strands are shown in Figure 8 with experimental data measured at various temperatures. The master curve shows a smooth decreasing single curve with increasing failure time.

σ_0 [MPa]	α	n_R	m_R	α_f	a [10 ⁻⁴]	b [10 ⁻⁴]	c [10 ⁻⁴]
3,721	27	0.0601	0.28	45	2.28	8.38	1.00

Table 3: Parameters of statistical static, creep, and fatigue strengths for CFRP strand.

Figure 8: Master curve of static strength of CFRP strand at $T = 120 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

5 STATISTICALLY INFERRED CREEP STRENGTH OF CFRP STRANDS

Creep failure tests of CFRP strands were conducted at three constant stress levels and one constant temperature $T = 120\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Results of the creep failure tests are presented in Figure 9. Tensile creep strength σ_c of CFRP strand is obtained using Equation 10. The predicted creep failure probability against the failure time calculated using substituting the parameters on Table 3 in Equation (4) is also shown in Figure 9. The predicted statistical creep failure time agrees well with the experimental data. Therefore, results clarified that the statistical creep failure time can be predicted from the master curve of creep compliance of matrix resin shown in Figure 4 and the parameters for statistical static strength of CFRP strands shown in Table 3.

Figure 9: Creep strength and failure probability against failure time at $T = 120\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

6 STATISTICALLY INFERRED FATIGUE STRENGTH OF CFRP STRANDS

Fatigue tension tests for CFRP strands were conducted at five temperature of $25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $120\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, $135\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and $150\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ with frequency $f = 2\text{ Hz}$ and the stress ratio of minimum stress/maximum stress $R = 0.1$. Tensile fatigue strength σ_f of CFRP strand is obtained using Equation (10). The number of cycles to failure N_f was measured through testing. Figure 10 shows the fatigue strength versus the number of cycles to failure for the CFRP strands at various maximum loads and temperatures. The fatigue strengths of CFRP strands decrease markedly with increase of the number of cycles to failure and temperature.

The dimensionless fatigue strength of CFRP strand is defined as shown by the following equation.

$$\log S_f = \log \frac{\sigma_f}{\sigma_0} - n_R \log \left[\frac{E_f^*(t, T)}{E_f(t_0, T_0)} \right] \tag{11}$$

Figure 11 shows the relation between the dimensionless fatigue strength S_f and the number of cycles to failure N_f . This relation clarifies only one curve that is independent of temperature. It is definable that this curve is the S–N master curve for CFRP strand. This curve is shown by the polynomial function of Equation (9). These parameters a , b , and c are shown in Table 3. Therefore, it is clear that the statistical fatigue strength at an arbitrary time, temperature, and frequency under pulsating load can be predicted from the master curve of creep compliance of matrix resin shown in Figure 4 and the parameters for statistical static and fatigue strengths of CFRP strands shown in Table 3.

Figure 10: Fatigue strengths of CFRP strand against number of cycles to failure.

Figure 11: S-N master curve of CFRP strand.

7 WEIBULL DISTRIBUTIONS OF STATIC, CREEP, AND FATIGUE STRENGTHS

The measured static strength $\sigma_s(i)$ for n specimens at an arbitrary failure time t and temperature T can be converted to dimensionless static strength $S_{s0}(i)$, as shown by the following equation.

$$\log S_{s0}(i) = \log \frac{\sigma_s(i)}{\sigma_0} - n_R \log \left[\frac{E_s^*(t, T)}{E_r(t_0, T_0)} \right], \quad i = 1 \sim n \quad (12)$$

The measured creep failure time $t(i)$ for n specimens at an arbitrary creep stress σ_c and temperature T can also be converted to the dimensionless creep strength $S_{c0}(i)$, as shown by the following equation.

$$\log S_{c0}(i) = \log \frac{\sigma_c}{\sigma_0} - n_R \log \left[\frac{E_c^*(t(i), T)}{E_r(t_0, T_0)} \right], \quad i = 1 \sim n \quad (13)$$

The number of cycles to failure $N_f(i)$ and failure time $t(i)$ measured for each test condition for fatigue strength σ_f , frequency f and temperature T can be converted to the dimensionless fatigue strength $S_{f0}(i)$ at $N_f = 1/2$, as shown by the following equation.

$$\log S_{f0}(i) = \log \frac{\sigma_f}{\sigma_0} - n_R \log \left[\frac{E_f^*(t(i), T)}{E_r(t_0, T_0)} \right] + F_f [\log(2N_f(i))], \quad t(i) = N_f(i)/f, \quad i = 1 \sim n \quad (14)$$

The Weibull distributions of the dimensionless static, creep, and fatigue strengths S_{s0} , S_{c0} and S_{f0} for each test condition are shown in Figure 12. This figure presents that shape parameters for static and creep loads maintain an almost constant value for various test conditions. However, the parameter α_f for fatigue strength is slightly larger than those for static and creep strengths and the parameter α_f is equal to 47 as shown on Table 3. Additionally, as this figure shows, the static and fatigue strengths at $T = 150^\circ\text{C}$ do not fit to the formulation curves because the straight lines of Weibull distributions for these strengths are separated by great distance from the cross points.

Figure 12: Weibull distributions of dimensionless static, creep, and fatigue strengths of CFRP strand.

8 COMPARISON BETWEEN CREEP AND FATIGUE STRENGTHS FOR CFRP STRANDS

All parameters for the statistical time and temperature dependent tensile static, creep, and fatigue strengths for CFRP strands are determined as shown on Table 3. Then, the predicted curves of statistical tensile creep and fatigue strengths can be constructed by substituting these parameters into Equations (4) and (7). Figure 13 portrays predicted curves against time and the number of cycles to

failure at high temperature with the measured data. These figures clarify that the time and temperature dependent behavior of creep strength differs considerably from that of fatigue strength. The creep strength maintains a constant value at short time and low temperature; it decreases drastically with increasing time and temperature at longer time and higher temperatures as shown in the upper panel. However, the fatigue strength decreases with increasing number of cycles to failure in the same manner in the wide range of time and temperature, although the fatigue strength at $N_f = 1/2$ to be the static strength changes with time and temperature in the same manner as the static and creep strengths, as shown in the lower panel.

Figure 13: Comparison between creep and fatigue strengths for CFRP strand at high temperatures.

9 CONCLUSION

Formulation for the statistical time and temperature dependent static, creep and fatigue strengths for CFRP was proposed based on the matrix resin viscoelasticity. The validity of formulation was clarified experimentally for tension loading along the longitudinal direction of unidirectional CFRP using our developed CFRP strand system. Results clarified that the long-term creep and fatigue failure time of unidirectional CFRP under tension loading can be readily inferred statistically using the results of static tests at various temperatures and fatigue tests conducted at a reference temperature.

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